

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OFUMBI****FIRST NAME: MATHIAS****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Academic Writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-12)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-42)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
5. Chicago Style (EUCLID 2021, 43-57)

BASICS IN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

This response paper is intended to provide my deep reflections on the study materials provided on academic writing. Course pack (Period 1) presented the basics of academic writing with regard to academic Essay Writing, Punctuation, American Vs British English, Plagiarism, Style Guide, Chicago Style Manual, and Latin Abbreviations.

This paper reflects on five key concepts studied: academic essay writing, punctuation, plagiarism, style guide, and Chicago style manual. For each of these concepts, I describe my understanding of the concept and what I learned.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

My major takeaway from the chapter on Essay Writing is that academic writing is systematic, objective, and rule-based. It is systematic because it has steps, structure, style, and flow. It requires objectivity in presentation and evaluation of available evidence to support or reject the hypothesis (EUCLID 2021, 7). It is based on some rules; for example,

plagiarism is not allowed. Other authors' works or ideas used must be acknowledged through citing and referencing it (EUCLID 2021, 7).

I learned that literature review is the bedrock and thread which flows through all academic writings. It is through literature review that the author contextualizes his ideas and identifies the gaps in information or methodology which needs to be addressed (EUCLID 2021, 8). Literature review involves accurate representation of other authors' work and critical evaluation of the same.

I appreciated the idea of planning as critical in academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 7). It facilitates organization and efficiency in execution of the research process. It enables the researcher to think through the research process, identify the tasks to be performed, time, and resources required. However, research is an iterative endeavor which require continuous updating of the research plan for it to be a management tool.

I understood that research involves creative and critical thinking (EUCLID 2021, 9). This means that the researcher should be open minded and innovative in undertaking the research process. Research also involves analytical rigor to delineate its scope and evaluate the findings. However, creative and critical thinking skills are scarce because they are not taught but acquired through experience.

My unforgettable take away from this chapter is the idea of writing the introduction after the body and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 11). This is contrary to the orthodox teaching which emphasizes starting with the introduction before writing the body and conclusions. I have always found difficulties with this approach because by the time you complete the body and conclusion, some of the things you wrote earlier in the introduction would have become irrelevant or changed.

Overall, the chapter on essay writing taught me that academic writing is methodical. The thread which flows through the academic writing is the literature. It requires analytical rigor in presentation and writing the introduction after the body and conclusion.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

In academic writing, punctuation is vital because it gives clarity to the message being communicated in a sentence. Every sentence must be punctuated. However, only essential punctuation should be made to clarify the meaning of the sentence (EUCLID 2021, 16). There are twelve punctuation marks: apostrophe, brackets, colon, semicolon, comma, dash, hyphen, ellipsis, full stop, exclamation mark, question mark, and quotation marks. I added my knowledge of application of some punctuation marks but still struggling with others. The trick I learned from reading the text is that if you are not sure of the correct punctuation marks to use, redraft the sentence.

I learnt from reading the text that apostrophe is used to show possession or contraction of some words. To indicate possession, apostrophe is used with s ('s) for singular nouns which do not end with the letter s. For example, Ofumbi's Response Paper.

Apostrophe can be used to show possession for some singular and plural nouns ending with letter s. For example, Mathias' Essay Paper or Boys' toilet (EUCLID 2021, 16). Apostrophe is also used in contraction of some word: don't (do not), can't (cannot), and it's (it is). However, in academic writing, using contracted words is not acceptable.

My understanding of colon and semicolon was in terms of the punctuation before listing and I used them interchangeably. For example, the reasons were as follows: I learned that a colon can be used to introduce a preceding phrase which is logically linked to the proceeding phrase (EUCLID 2021, 18). A colon can be used to connect two interdependent parts of the sentence. For example, the program had two components: water and sanitation. A semicolon, on the other hand, is used to connect independent clauses or parts of a sentence. Each part can stand on its own as an independent sentence. For example, in Uganda, education is expensive; children who go to public schools are from poor families.

I am still grappling with the understanding of the correct use of single and double quotation marks. In the course pack (EUCLID 2021, 23), it is stated that "use single quotation marks for direct speech or a quote and double quotation marks for direct speech or a quote within that." Conversely, the Turabian Manual of Writers (9th Edition) states that "for a quotation within a quotation, use single quotation marks for the inner set of quoted words." On page 49 of the course pack (EUCLID 2021), it is stated that "double quotes can be changed to single quotes, and vice versa, for merging the quote with the rest of the text." My take on these two positions is that the difference is in style, and Turabian application of single and double quotation marks is consistent with most literature on the same.

My memorable takeaway from the chapter on punctuation is the application of exclamation marks. I was taught to use exclamation marks to indicate something wonderful, and I have been religiously using it for that purpose. I have learned that an exclamation mark is used at the end of the direct speech. For example, come with me! Or wait for me! I have been using full stop instead of exclamation mark, and whenever I would encounter it in the literature used not in the context of showing something wonderful, I would regard it as wrong punctuation.

Generally, I found the chapter on punctuation very useful because there was a lot of learning and unlearning. I learned that in the application of the different punctuation marks, the context matters. However, the EUCLID application of double quotation marks for inner quotes within a quotation, contrary to the conventional practice in the literature of using single quotation marks for inner quotes, needs further research. I will forever remember to use exclamation marks for direct speech.

4) PLAGIARISM

In academic writing, plagiarism is a serious offense. It involves using other authors' works without recognizing them. I learned that copying, quoting, and paraphrasing other authors' words or ideas without citing them is plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34). I noted

that using other authors' work is not an offense as long as you cite them through in-text citations and a list of works cited. The in-text citation must indicate the author's surname, year, and page number where the information was obtained. The list of works cited is references or a bibliography at the end of the paper or research report. It provides the names of the authors, year, title of the article, volume number, publisher, place and year of publication, and page numbers where the information was obtained. The exact contents of the reference depend on the standard adopted (Turabian, APA, or CMS).

I learned about short and long quotations. Short quotations are less than five lines, and long or block quotations are more than five lines. Short quotations are in-text (within the paragraph) and must be enclosed with quotation marks (double or single). Block quotations start on a new paragraph, not enclosed in quotation marks, and the paragraph is indented, not at the same margin as the rest of the paragraphs. At the end of every quote, the source of information must be cited. I learned that quotations should be limited to the essential ones providing strong evidence to support your findings or argument.

I learned that in academic writing, you do not use other author's words. You are supposed to borrow their ideas and use your own words to articulate them. You can paraphrase some of the ideas and information using your own language and style of writing different from the other authors. The author's ideas must be accurately represented. Each paragraph should be properly cited using in-text citation except where the information is common knowledge.

Overall, the chapter on plagiarism taught me not to copy other authors' work and use it as if it were mine. I learned that whenever I use other authors' works: I should borrow their ideas, articulate them using my own words and properly cite them.

5) STYLE GUIDE

The concept of the Style Guide was new to me, but I found it very useful. I learned that a style guide is necessary for documenting the elements of style you want to use in writing your paper. The style guide, if you follow it, ensures consistency and internal coherence of the document. The basic elements of the writing style guide are language (US or UK English), punctuation, font type and size, layout of the paper, length of sentences and paragraphs, use of abbreviations, vocabulary, citation, and referencing (EUCLID 2021, 41).

I learned that there is no standard writing style guide for academic writing. However, some Universities, Professional Associations, and Publishers have developed manuals or guidelines. These can be reference materials when developing your style guide. In developing the guide, the requirements of the consumer or University must be considered. For example, EUCLID recommends the use of Chicago Style (EUCLID 2021, 41).

Overall, a style guide is a useful tool for academic writers if it is well thought through and followed. However, the lack of a standardized academic writing style guide

means that there will always be a debate on the application of certain elements of style. This means that the writer must be flexible to make adjustments to the style guides as necessary. The message is consistency in writing your paper.

6) CHICAGO STYLE

Chicago Style is a way of formatting research papers and books using the Chicago Manual of Style. I learned from the Chicago style that in academic writing, abbreviations that are not acronyms or initialisms should seldom be used (EUCLID 2021, 44). Scholarly abbreviations can be used but in parenthesis to provide additional information. Examples of scholarly abbreviations are, e.g., i.e., etc.,. When these abbreviations are used outside the parenthesis, then they should be written in full. I also learned that an acronym must be introduced the first time it is used. For example, UNICEF (United Nations Children Fund).

Another element of style I learned was Capitalization. I have been grappling with what should be capitalized in the headings and sentences. The Chicago Style has three forms of capitalization: full capitalization, heading capitalization, and sentence capitalization. For full capitalization, all words are formatted in upper case. This form of capitalization is used for titles or chapter or section headings. Heading capitalization involves formatting in upper case the first letter of the first word, nouns, pronouns, and adjectives. I learned that articles (e.g., a), prepositions (e.g., between), conjunctions (e.g., and), and infinitives (e.g., to) are not supposed to be capitalized. For sentence capitalization: capitalize the first letter of the first word and after the colon, and proper nouns.

I also learned that when you use a quotation that has an unfamiliar word or concept, then use (sic) to mean that the original text is being quoted faithfully. Chicago style allows editing of quotes with regard to quotation marks, capitalization, punctuation, typographic errors, and emphasis. However, the editing should not change the original meaning of the quotation or message therein.

7) CONCLUSION

This course pack was intended to equip the students with the basics of academic writing with regard to essay writing, punctuation, plagiarism, and rules of style. I can attest that the material in this course pack is very useful and will remain my reference material for academic writing. The chapter on essay writing taught me that academic writing is methodical, grounded in literature review, and applies analytical rigor in presentation. I learned the correct application of some of the punctuations but also limited them by writing short sentences.

I learned that plagiarism is a serious academic offense committed when you use other authors' works without recognizing them. Copying other authors' work is not acceptable, but you can borrow their ideas and articulate them using your own words. I learned that a style guide is a management tool for academic writers to ensure consistency

and coherence in their writing. I found the Chicago Style Manual a useful reference in academic writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*. Ninth Edition. Chicago. University of Chicago Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.